

Peristeriones: An architecture not made for people?

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Introduction

Many colleagues respond very skeptically when learning about research done into the architecture of dovecotes on a Greek island. Such an enterprise may seem of secondary importance when compared with many of today's challenges to architects — such as solving the ever increasing housing problem almost everywhere in the world, facing the inhumanity of cities, or limit-

ing the ecological damage caused by profit-oriented planning and building. However, a sane balance between art and science, between the right and left side of the brain or between delight and concern is only the expression of a comprehensive understanding of reality, and indeed a matter of sustainable development. In a complex world apparently minor issues can act as an important catalyst in crucial social or natural processes. In this context the study of the Tinean *Peristeriones* (in the singular, *Peristerion*) — as the pigeon houses or dovecotes are called on this Cycladic island — attains a new meaning.¹

Every visitor to the island of Tinos will soon notice the extreme beauty and high number of the *Peristeriones* — buildings that may also be defined as pigeon towers because of their considerable height compared to the surface they cover. Certainly, structures serving the same purpose can also be found on other Aegean islands or in much more distant places such as Egypt or Persia. But nowhere else is an equally high number of them concentrated on such a small territory — the island covers not more than 195 sq.km (fig. 1) — or built in the same decorative manner displaying considerably more elaboration than the

Fig. 1: Map of the island of Tinos. (Copyright Kosta Mathéy).

modest houses being lived in by the resident population. To architectural historians this phenomenon poses the double question about the motivations for the extraordinary ornamentation and the high frequency of dovecotes in Tinos.

My systematic photographic survey and mapping of all Peristeriones in Tinos identified a total number of 1,179 — a result similar to the one revealed by a previous but unpublished study by the Swiss architect Manuel Baud-Bovy in the 1950s. Only very recently a number of Peristeriones perished due to natural decay or intentional destruction dictated by road construction schemes — sadly enough cars are valued higher than the unique cultural heritage by the island's administration. This circumstance calls for international lobbying for conservation apart from the purely scientific interest in the architecture.

This paper describes the structure and appearance of the Tinean Peristeriones before attempting an interpretation of their form, number and distribution.

Elements of form variation

No single Peristerion is the same as another. However, the common stylistic elements between them are sufficient for an expert eye to distinguish the Tinean Peristerion from the pigeon houses in other regions — a fair justification for referring to it as local or "indigenous" architecture.

The architecture of each Peristerion follows simple rules incorporating a limited number of variations in plan, height, elevation and roof toppings. This limitation in formal expression to basically four variables with not more than two dozen patterns each nevertheless allows a high artistic fascination. Monotony can be easily avoided since all theoretically possible combinations must be millions. In the following, the variables with their typical patterns are discussed.

● **Plan and size:** Apart from three or four Peristeriones that are of circular layout as they have been installed in transformed windmills, all other Peristeriones have a rectangular plan and no internal walls. Because of the notoriously strong winds on the island two of the walls may be extended into projecting pillars in order to shelter the access holes for the birds in the facade (fig. 2). The ground floor is normally used for storing agricultural

Fig. 2: Island of Tinos — Ground plans of Peristeriones.

Fig. 3: Island of Tinos — Construction of a Peristerion.

Fig. 4: Island of Tinos — Rear view of a Peristerion.

tools, since the Peristeriones can be found scattered across the fields sometimes far from the villages. A hole in the ceiling gives access to the upper room where the pigeons are kept, and where breeding nests are incorporated in the walls in the form of niches. The depth of the room is determined by the length of the traditionally available timber beams on the island, and rarely exceeds 3 m. The beams support natural stone slabs forming ceiling and roof; the latter was additionally covered by a layer of seaweed (for insulation) and clay (for waterproofing). The Peristeriones' outside image appears somehow bigger because the dry stone walls are between 50 and 100 cm thick (fig. 3).

● **The facade:** The walls of a Peristerion can be left bare or treated as an ornamental facade. On the side facing the mountain not much care is taken to enhance the visual impact; at the most some projecting stones serve as a ladder facilitating access to the roof which needs regular maintenance² (fig. 4). The part of the front facade which belongs to the upper floor of the Peristerion incorporates the entrance holes for the pigeons and tends to be divided into horizontal stripes of ornaments formed from flat stone slabs (fig. 5). Also one or both side elevations can be treated in the same manner. The ornamentation is typically composed of squares, triangles, circles or wheels. Less frequent motives include the cypress tree or tree of life, twigs or fish bones, the caro, and — exceptionally — also

Fig. 5: Island of Tinos — The facade is structured into horizontal ornamental stripes.

Fig. 6: Island of Tinos — The basic ornamental elements of the facade.

letters and numbers (figs. 6 and 7).

The entrance holes are located in the lower part of the ornamentation. A projecting stone board is fixed underneath; this facilitates the landing of the pigeons in the first place but is also

intended to inhibit snakes from entering the Peristerion.³

● **Toppings:** Another characteristic, probably even older than the frontal ornamentation, are objects or sculptures placed on the roof of the Peristerion (fig. 8). Early examples take the form

Fig. 7: Island of Tinos — Ornamental facade of a Peristerion.

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of silhouettes and statues, whereas more modern variations tend to be abstract or repeat the ornamentation of the facade (figs. 9 and 10).

● **Location and orientation:** Most Peristeriones have been erected at the edge of the fields which form terraces in the mountainous terrain (fig. 11). Thus, the birds' rich manure, which

Legends

Fig. 8: Island of Tinos — Taxonomy of ornamental toppings.

Fig. 9: Island of Tinos — The silhouette of a woman's head belongs to the older ornamental toppings found.

Fig. 10: Island of Tinos — Abstract motives are the most common kind of rooftop ornamentation of Peristeriones.

Fig. 11: Island of Tinos — Most Peristeriones are located among the fields.

accumulates in the Peristeriones, can be made use of to fertilize the soil. Pigeon droppings, which contain phosphorus, have also been known to be collected for the fabrication of gunpowder in some cultures such as in Persia or Britain⁴; but in Tinos this does not seem to have been practiced.

Only rarely are Peristeriones incorporated into normal houses within a village, where the birds would cause unwanted noise and dirt. Also in the stony and unfertile mountain regions in the north and west of the island Peristeriones were almost never built.

Possible interpretations

An accurate description and documentation of an architectural phenomenon like the Tinean Peristeriones is a rewarding task particularly since these buildings may disappear forever. However, for the socially oriented researcher other questions remain to be answered. After all, Greece is renowned for extraordinary building crafts since ancient times. This tradition suggests a deeper meaning behind the elaborate vernacular architecture of the Peristeriones. What had their constructors in mind when designing them?

Numerous interviews, observations and literature evaluation suggest multiple approaches to interpreting the Peristeriones' architecture. Apart from the obvious functional needs arising from the job of pigeon breeding, additional formal influences can be identified arising from the material used, from the island's history, from local handicraft patterns, from religion, mysticism, economy and the social formation.

● **Form follows function?** Every builder will need to observe the functional needs of the intended building, and this will have an impact on its form. In the case of the Peristeriones the practical requirements are simple: the pigeons must be provided with a comfortable home and protected from potentially dangerous vermin like snakes and martens. Nestling niches must be provided to facilitate raising young birds. Since the pigeons like to rest in between their flying trips, the incorporation of multiple sitting options seems to be a good idea: they are in fact much used both in the case of the niches formed by the ornaments of the facade and of the toppings on the roofs. In several peasants' opinion, the latter are also intended to function as scarecrows to keep away bigger hunting birds. Therefore the sculptures and silhouettes portraying people, particularly applied in the western part of the island, make sense.

● **Using local building materials:** The director of the Athens Museum of Decorative Arts once explained to me: "the ornaments are determined by the material." Considering that thin stone slabs can be found locally, the basic ornaments — square, triangle and (segment of the) circle — seem to prove the statement. After all, they represent the three most obvious options to form an opening in a wall: a horizontal beam (square), two inclined slabs supporting each other (triangle),⁵ and the arch (semicircle) (fig. 12). The fields formed in such a way can be subdivided further with the same material, or closed off with a plate. The second option is a typical feature of residential architecture in Tinos, and is traditionally done with a carved piece of marble, the other local stone (fig. 13) apart from the slate. These often very elaborate plates are known as *kamari* or *hyperthiro*, but round rosettes and square forms can occasionally be found on the facades of Peristeriones, too (fig. 14).

However, the hypothesis about the ornaments induced by the building material apart from functional needs is not fully conclusive, either. For example, it does not explain why these ornaments were mostly applied on the parts of a facade where no opening needs to be bridged, or why the same ornaments have been used elsewhere with completely different material. In other words, this explanation only holds to a certain extent, but other decisive factors are likely to be present, too.

Fig. 12: Island of Tinos — The use of local building materials can explain the preference of certain ornamental forms.

Fig. 13: Island of Tinos — Local stone slabs used for forming the typical ornaments of a Peristerion.

Fig. 14: Island of Tinos — *Hyperthiro* or *kamari* applied to a Peristerion.

● **Traditional and folkloric arts:** Some of the ornaments mentioned, such as squares, wheels, cypresses, are also common in other fields of Greek popular art, particularly in wood carvings, i.e. on chests or cooking spoons, in stitching and embroidering on clothes, or in the masonry of tombstones.⁵ This observation suggests that a spontaneous desire for decoration may have been an equally or maybe even more important feature in the Peristerion's ornaments than the material alone. The ones encountered imitate elements of an ever present nature: the wheel recalls the sun's rays or the flowers in the fields; the cypress and the twigs refer to trees in general; the square can be read as a sign for crystalline stone, but also for a winding river which was visualized in the meander friezes since ancient times. The less abstract roof toppings can portray people or birds (fig. 15). But what about the purely architectural features of the facades, which do not appear in the folkloric arts, nor have anything to do with the building material, and are different from dovecotes (same function!) elsewhere?

● **Architectural fashion and local history:** Remembering that the Peristeriones described are unique to Tinos,⁷ particular historical events may be worth mentioning when looking at architectural particularities. Above all, an outstanding historical fact is the uninterrupted Venetian occupation from 1207 until 1714 — longer than in any other part of Greece. Together with Venetian governors, Western European architectural concepts and fashions arrived in Greece. This is particularly true for interior design since furniture is more easily transportable than complete houses and hence was often imported. One obvious stylistic element adopted by the Peristeriones this way is their strong frontality, including the untreated back elevation — just like a piece of furniture to be placed against the wall. In the second half of the last century, the time when most of the Peristeriones were built in Tinos, neo-classic was the style in fashion. From this origin we recognize the symmetric facade, the elevated base storey, the attic, the pillars, and sculptures on the roof (figs. 16 and 17). By the way, some of these features can also be found on the houses of the local aristocracy, but never on the peasants' houses in the villages.

● **Religion:** People in Tinos are very religious — there are even more chapels scattered around the island than there are Peristeriones. Although the principal religion is Orthodoxy, the Catholic community is also strong, a heritage from the Venetian occupation.⁸ It is very likely that the construction of pigeon houses was propelled by the Catholic priests, since keeping pigeons was a habit in many European monasteries and mansions. In Tinos at least one Peristerion can be clearly identified to have belonged to a Catholic priest: the letters in the decorative facade come from the Roman and not the common Greek alphabet (fig. 18).

Many Peristeriones have a cross incorporated in the facade, which reminds one of the churches where it symbolizes both the crucifixion of Jesus Christ and the four evangelists. A religious meaning is also linked to the triangle (STUHLFAUTH, 1937): the Holy Trinity unites God the Father, Jesus Christ and the Holy Spirit (whereas the latter is occasionally symbolized in the form of a pigeon, with reference to the Bible (JOHN 1, 32-34) — an important connotation for somebody building a pigeon house!). The superposition of two triangles makes the star of David — symbolizing the combination of earth and heaven (BAUER et al., 1992) — but also the six days in which the world was created.

Sometimes the triangle is shown with a vertical line in the middle, dividing it into two Pythagorean triangles — which in their turn occasionally stand for duality in nature (similar to the Yin-and-Yang motive in Eastern thought), or the balance between sun and moon. The moon, on the other hand, identifies the Virgin Mary in the same way as the sun symbolized her son Jesus Christ (hence the linguistic proximity between sun and son in most Indo-Germanic languages). The old code name IXΘΥΣ

Fig. 15: Island of Tinos — Forms of nature as an ornamental motive applied to the Peristeriones.

Fig. 16: Elements of neo-classical architecture.

Fig. 17: Island of Tinos — Peristerion with neo-classical stylistic elements.

Fig. 18: Island of Tinos — Peristerion with an ornamental facade incorporating Latin letters.

Fig. 19: Island of Tinos — Peristerion with fish bone motives on the facade.

Fig. 20: Island of Tinos — Religious motives incorporated in the Peristerion's ornamentation.

Fig. 21: Island of Tinos — Inter-numeral relationships in nature and the universe.

Fig. 22: Island of Tinos — Symbolism and the basic tree ornamental pattern of the Peristeriones.

(ICHTHYS) for Jesus Christ also means “fish” in ancient Greek — considering this, the appearance of the fishbone motive on some Peristeriones’ ornamentation is perhaps no coincidence (fig. 19). The duplication of the hexagon produces a 12-star, which not only recalls the 12 apostles but also the 12 months of the year. The 12-star contains, of course, the cross again and simultaneously incorporates the duality in the contraction and expansion of the days in the four seasons which make up the 12 months.

In some parts of Tinos it is possible to find Peristeriones with a division of the facade into three axes. This division is also a common element in church design, particularly in the plan, the apse, and the *ikonostasis* of Orthodox churches. The multiple religious interpretations of the Peristeriones’ ornamentation are visualized in figure 20.

● **Cosmos:** The manifold relationships between the numbers four, six, eight and twelve form part of traditional understanding of nature. For example, the four elements are identified as air, fire, water, and earth in Western civilization, but in the East understood differently as sentiments arising in the combination of the ones mentioned: hot (air + fire), dry (fire + earth), cold (earth + water), and wet (water + air). The synthesis from the eight, Eastern and Western, elements makes the ether, or the universe. The 12-star, eventually, incorporates the numbers four, six, and eight, and is therefore considered a magic number. It reappears in the counting of the day’s hours, in the months, in the constellations, but also in the twelve tribes of Israel⁹ (fig. 21) (CRITCHLOW, 1969 and 1976).

● **Mysticism and symbolism:** The three basic motives of the Peristeriones’ ornamentation — circle, triangle, and square — have similar symbolic connotations in many cultures (fig. 22). They represent heaven, man and earth (or the material world). The triangle can be drawn with one corner above or below. In the first case it stands for man, in the second for woman. In alchemy the same two orientations mean fire and water (BAUER et al., 1991). With a shorter base — apparently the earliest ornament used on a Peristerion — it can visualize the Tree of Life (fig. 23). The superposition of circle, triangle, and square is the home of man — the house in nature.

Several references to pigeons can be found in Greek mythology. Zeus, for example, is said to have been raised in his childhood by pigeons in a cave, and transformed himself into a pigeon to mate with Phthia (POLLARD, 1977; THOMPSON, 1895). Also the goddess Semiramis, daughter of Derketo (Aphrodite), is believed to have been nursed by pigeons, with the result that upon her death she became a pigeon and flew away in a flock of pigeons. But even before the time of Greek mythology the pigeon had strong symbolic connotations. Both for the Phoenicians and in Asia Minor the pigeon was associated with Istar, the goddess of fertility. In ancient Greece this goddess was

Fig. 23: Island of Tinos — The triangle with a short base symbolizes the Tree of Life.

known as Aphrodite, and was frequently portrayed in sculptures holding a pigeon in her hand. Hence the name *Peristera* for pigeon and *Peristerion* for a pigeon house evolved (POLLARD, 1977).¹⁰

Also Islamic religion worships the pigeon, believing that this bird protected Mohammed when seeking refuge. The present and international meaning as a symbol of peace has its origin in the Old Testament: it reports Noah to have sent out a pigeon as a messenger; the same bird returned with an olive twig in its mouth — the sign of God's forgiveness (LAMER, 1933; POLLARD, 1977).

Beyond the ornament

As demonstrated so far, the typical ornamentation of the Tinean Peristeriones can be interpreted in multiple ways. No single explanation is conclusive enough to be valid on its own; but all interpretations are directly or indirectly interconnected. Natural phenomena have been internalized by mankind in mystic, symbolic and religious rules. The beauty of nature and the trust in the signs of belief have stimulated local artists and artisans to apply certain symbols in the decoration of their products. Certain elements, like the silhouettes of people meant to function as scarecrows, conform with popular belief and are valid arguments in understanding vernacular architecture — even if they may not withstand a scientific analysis. An important insight might be that popular architecture incorporates and synthesizes many aspects of their builder's culture simultaneously, and is rarely a product of rational design. In this it differs from what architects claim from their products.

Having gained a certain understanding of the meaning behind the Tinean Peristeriones' decorative elements, the second question remains still unanswered: Why were these objects believed so important that so much care was given to decorating them at all? Furthermore, the high concentration of Peristeriones on one small island requires an explanation. Both questions are probably closely linked and may lead to the same answer. Although absolute certainty will probably never be gained, my conclusions hint at economic and social reasons. In the following I will further expand on this question.

● **Pigeon raising:** Today pigeon raising has become a hobby in many parts of the world, including Tinos. This hobby refers, however, to a long tradition with originally economic motivation (BEAZLEY, 1966; BEATON, 1977; HANCOCKS, 1971; KAMMERMEIER, 1978). One benefit certainly is the availability of pigeon meat as man's food, which helps to supplement the often meager diet in poorer and isolated regions.¹¹ Thompson (1895) reports that on the Cycladic islands pigeon meat was consumed in quantities in the last century. But for reasons to be explained below, pigeons were never a typical poor people's food; and apart from that there are other motives for keeping doves.

Already in ancient times pigeons were raised in Greece, where they were probably imported by the Persian troops.¹² Aristotle and other ancient writers tell us that pigeons were also favorite gifts between lovers and that they tended to appear in erotic dreams — because they represent chastity and fidelity. On Delos, a neighboring island to Tinos, pigeons were kept 2,000 years ago, as the saying "Dilios Kolumbidis" reveals. Plato even explains how to build a pigeon house in his *Geoponica* (XIV.6, quoted in POLLARD, 1977).

As mentioned before, the long Venetian domination over Tinos may be partly responsible for the habit of pigeon raising there. Already the ancient Romans were known for their fashion of keeping pigeons, as Pliny reaffirms (quoted in KELLER, 1909); and this habit was apparently long-lived because almost every Italian Renaissance mansion incorporates a dovecote in its plan. Apart from the culinary value the Romans depended on the

pigeons for communication in their huge empire — a practice already known in Babylon and among Saracen warriors (SACY, 1805; THOMPSON, 1895).¹³ It seems a convincing argument that the Venetian governors in Tinos similarly relied on pigeon mail to communicate with their homeland and that this contributed to a high number of pigeons on the island.

Tinos is also renowned for the fertility of its fields, although its geological composition does not differ greatly from neighboring islands (LACROIX, 1881). Apart from the availability of water,¹⁴ fertilization with pigeon manure may have played its part in this.¹⁵ Pigeon manure production was also of direct economic importance since Tinos used to export it in the past, and derived a certain wealth from it.

● **How old are the Peristeriones?** Given the long tradition of pigeon raising on Tinos one might assume an old origin of the Peristeriones. However, in spite of important ruins belonging to a Hellenistic temple and to the Venetian castle at the foot of the mountain Exombourgo, there are no indications of equally old Peristeriones. This does not preclude the existence of dovecotes in Tinos during those periods, but if those had been built with the same care as described above the archaeologists would certainly have noticed.

Specialists agree that most of today's existing Peristeriones date from the 19th and 20th centuries. The oldest Peristerion carrying a year date was built in 1837 and exposes very little ornamentation (fig. 24). Another indication for a rather recent habit of building elaborate Peristeriones is their concentration close to the present main village of Tinos (formerly known as Aghios Nicolaos). Although this place was already important in ancient times because of the temple of Poseidon and the harbor belonging to it, the area was deserted in the Middle Ages because of the threat of pirate attacks: the residents had withdrawn to the mountains preferably in locations invisible from the sea.¹⁶ For the same reason the facades remained unpainted; the fashion of whitewashing them — which today appears to be a synonym for the architecture of the Cycladic islands — was only prescribed by the Papadopoulos dictatorship in the 1960s to promote tourism. Today even some Peristeriones have been erroneously whitewashed, but the beautiful slate ornaments become invisible when plastered and tend to be spared for that reason.

● **Pilgrimages to Tinos:** Today's main village of the island began to grow only in the 19th century at the time of the Greek liberation movement. During this period, exactly in 1822, a nun of the convent known as Monastiri today happened to find a miraculous icon in the fields. When the news spread, thousands of pilgrims flocked into Tinos. The Turkish rulers tolerated Christian religious activities in the occupied territories. However, the Greek nationalist movement was primarily fuelled by the Orthodox Church. The pilgrimages were a good pretext for the clergy to meet without raising the Turks' suspicion and to discuss political strategies. Fate was wise to choose Tinos for the miracle, since the place also possessed important strategic properties to become a symbol for a new and free Greece: it was the island that, due to the Venetians' presence, had resisted Turkish occupation longer than any other place; Delos, once the seat of the powerful ancient Delian League, was close enough to be visually present — while now unpopulated and useless for big gatherings. Equally in viewing distance was Ermoupolis, on the island of Syros, the most important harbor of the Aegean at the time and much bigger than Athens. But Syros was the residence of a Catholic archbishop and too problematic for Orthodox expansion.

Massive pilgrimages, which still nowadays gather around the 25th March¹⁷ and the 15th August every year, soon brought an unusually high number of visitors to the island. Travel reports of the period mention some 45,000 pilgrims — more than twice the resident population of the whole island. Dove raising and the erection of so many Peristeriones close to the main village of

Fig. 24: Island of Tinos — Oldest dated Peristerion: 1837.

Tinos can be linked to the pilgrimages by several means: various services granted to the visitors provided an important income for the local folk; a turnover equivalent to 20,000 Pounds Sterling was reported by Bent (1885).¹⁸ Even the pigeons themselves played their part in this business: Bent not only mentions a flourishing trade from the sale of pigeons, but also tells us how these birds had been trained to pick small letters telling fortunes out of a wooden box.¹⁹ It must also be recalled that most pilgrims came to Tinos to be healed from a disease. The medical application of pigeons' hearts, blood, feathers and excrement has been known in all epochs.²⁰ Given the religious connotations

of doves, building precious Peristeriones must have contributed to the owners' and the island's prestige.

One particular Peristerion in the more remote northern part of the island is particularly interesting stylistically because its ornaments were applied only later on, and are not part of the original construction (fig. 25). This seems to be an indication of the ornamentation of the Peristeriones becoming a fashion at a certain point in time. It is also worth mentioning that the Peristeriones tend to be particularly richly decorated where many of them stand near each other, as in the proximity of the village of Smardaki. Apparently some kind of competition among

Fig. 25: Island of Tinos — Peristerion with ornaments fixed at a later period.

the owners for the most beautiful Peristerion in the valley had developed.

● **Status and economy:** There is another connection between wealth and ownership of a pigeon house. Doves are hungry birds and eat, among other things, the wheat from the fields. On the other hand, landownership is a privilege commonly enjoyed by the better-off; and these want to make sure that it is their own pigeon population that seeks nourishment in the fields. Therefore almost everywhere in the world the possession and operation of a dovecote used to be highly regulated and restricted — at least as long as the social formation could be identified by a peasant society. In England, for example, a landlord could own and even lease out a dovecote. On the other hand, the death penalty was declared for anybody else killing one of his doves (CROOKE, 1920; JEEVAR, 1976). Also in France, the right to a pigeon house was restricted to the big landowners; later the clergy were included, too (HANCOCKS, 1971).

I have not seen any original sources documenting a similar ruling for Tinos; but Vallianou and Vokou (1986) assume that such a restriction also applied to Tinos until the ruling was cancelled by the Turks upon their arrival on the island in the late 18th century: from then on everybody was permitted to own a Peristerion. This period coincides with the beginning of economic prosperity due to the trade with Constantinople, but also to the pilgrimages as outlined above. The affluence propelled, for example, the construction of numerous new churches in the villages of Tinos. It seems very likely that once the privilege of owning a Peristerion was “popularized,” many of those who could afford so, desired to make use of it. This might have contributed to the massive appearance of Peristeriones in the 19th century.

Conclusion

A variety of complementary explanations for the form and concentration of Peristeriones on Tinos have been proposed so far. Other than for example in the context of engineering, in social sciences one is unlikely to encounter only one single valid explanation to a question, since human actions are guided by logic, intuition, feelings, belief and coincidence alike. But architecture also has to do with art, which has little to do with science. Albeit based on empirical observation, numerous interviews and literature evaluation over more than ten years, the findings presented remain speculative in several respects. Of course, the availability of original documents would have been helpful. However, in the case of old vernacular architecture we lack the direct information from the builders who often were not able to write and could not leave a testimony; for oral communication they lived too long ago. Anyway, we have to accept that many aspects of life cannot, and should not, be fully explained.

Notes

1. The terms “dove” and “pigeon” are used interchangeably in this article.
2. The surface is kept smooth by periodically levelling it with a stone roll.
3. Tinos has a tremendous snake population; this is why it was called Ophioussa — the snake island — in ancient times. Some authors assume that the name Tinos is derived from the Phoenician word “tanoth” which means “snake” — and that, in return, the name “tenia” for “viper” refers to “Tinos.” In any case, snakes were even printed on the antique coins issued on the island — with reference to the sanctuary of Asclepius, whose ruins can still be visited on the island today (LACROIX, 1881; MURRAY, 1840).
4. To make gunpowder, pigeon manure is mixed with lime and ash (FRYER, n.d.; SUFFIELD-JONES, 1966).
5. The most famous example of the use of two inclined slabs to bridge a gap, thus forming a triangle, is certainly the Lion Gate in Mycenae,

the Peloponnese, Greece.

6. Tombstones in Tinean cemeteries often display a Tree of Life together with pigeons. In ancient times pigeons were also valued as a sacrifice to death. This habit may be connected to the Syrian tradition of erecting pigeon towers on top of graves (KELLER, 1909).
7. Pigeon houses can also be found on other islands not far from Tinos, in particular on Mykonos, Andros and Sifnos. However, there they tend to be less elaborate and are definitely much fewer in number.
8. The Catholic clergy gained a special merit by improving the education of the peasants, including women who were taught by the Ursuline nuns.
9. The twelve tribes of Israel are the origin of the twelve apostles, see above.
10. The Greek noun “Peristera” is composed from the semitic words “perach”-“ister,” which means “bird of Istar.” In different cultures the goddess Istar or Aphrodite was worshipped as Astarte, Atargatis, or Derketo (KELLER, 1909).
11. 300 years ago, a total number of 26,000 dovecotes providing pigeon meat were reported in England alone (BEATON, 1977).
12. According to Pherecrates (LAMER, 1933; POLLARD, 1977). Beazley (1966) mentions another source from the beginning of the 19th century, which describes the pigeon towers in Persia where they were built much more beautifully than the people’s residences — as, similarly, in Tinos!
13. Aristophanes also describes the raising of postal pigeons (POLLARD, 1977).
14. In ancient times Tinos was also known under the name Hydroussa, which means “the one with plenty of water” (MURRAY, 1900).
15. The excellent fertilizing quality of pigeon manure has been explained by the inefficient digestive system of the birds.
16. In 1676-1678 only a few isolated houses could be found at the harbor (BENT, 1885; MURRAY, 1884). The pirates only disappeared from the Aegean sea with the Turkish occupation and their constant military presence at the end of the 18th century.
17. Apart from the religious festivities the same day has become Greek Independence Day!
18. The island’s wealth did not arise from the pilgrimages alone: various sources describing Tinos before the revolution mention a flourishing production of silk and gloves (FRIESMANN, 1793; KINSBERGEN, 1792).
19. There is an age-old linkage between doves and fortune-telling, which was reported inter alia from the Greek oracles in Dodona in Epirus and Thebes in Boeotia (ARNETH, 1841; KELLER, 1909; THOMPSON, 1895).
20. The medical use of pigeons has been described by Pollard (1977) and Thompson (1895). Tinos also had an Temple of Asclepius, but there are no reports of whether doves were involved in the activities of the sanctuary.

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